

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING L2 AND CULTURE

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Abstract. This article is devoted to reveal the role of digital technologies in teaching L2. Also, it discusses place of digital technologies in the culture, and determines how beneficial or harmful they are to human life

Key words: digital technologies, educational apps, memrise, duolingo, teacher's role, society, culture.

Introduction. These days in each branch of our life is changing into connected with digital technologies and it's not excepted from the method of education. throughout the education amount at faculties, universities or at kindergartens we have a tendency to use them as an academic tool. initial and foremost, it might be higher if we have a tendency to answer the subsequent question what's the digital technologies itself?

Digital technologies area unit electronic tools, devices, systems, and resources that generate, store or method knowledge. Digital tools embody social media, mobile phones, on-line games, and multimedia system. The effective use of digital learning

tools in lecture rooms will increase student engagement, facilitate lecturers improve their lesson plans, and facilitate personalized learning. It additionally helps students to create essential 21st-century skills.

Teachers need to develop student performance, and technology might facilitate them implement this goal. To mitigate the challenges, directors should facilitate lecturers collect the competencies required to boost learning for college students by technology. additionally, technology within the schoolroom ought to create teachers' jobs easier while not adding time beyond regulation to their day.

Technology provides learners with easy-to-access knowledge, accelerated learning, and fun possibilities to apply what they learn. It permits students to explore new subjects and deepen their comprehension of exhausting ideas, particularly in STEM. Through the alter of technology within and out of doors the schoolroom, students may gain 21st-century technical skills necessary for future occupations.

Still, kids learn additional effectively with instruction. the planet Economic Forum reports that whereas technology will facilitate young students learn and acquire data through play, as an example, proof suggests that learning is simpler through steerage from associate adult, like a coach.

Leaders and directors ought to size up of wherever their college area unit in terms of their understanding of on-line areas. From lessons learned throughout this troubled time, they'll implement solutions currently for the long run. as an example, directors might provide lecturers per week or 2 to think twice regarding the way to teach courses not antecedently on-line. Additionally, to a research of solutions, flexibility throughout these making an attempt times is of predominate importance.

The role of digital technologies in teaching foreign languages has been one of the most discussed topics in conferences not just in Russia, but also in the UK, having been published in various monographs. The visual aspect plays an important role in implementing digital technologies in education and visualisation therefore plays a vital role in education in various forms, from full-time education to distance

learning. Visualisation is closely integrated to distance or virtual learning, where a teacher does not serve as a guide, but preferably as a tutor, while incorporating different simulation processes aimed at developing speaking skills and critical thinking. Presentations are the most used devices for developing visualization, contributing to the formation of new original ideas, stimulating artistic imagination and enhancing the level of receptive and productive skills.

As a coach we are able to use some instructional apps to create effective progress in learning method and people apps embody telephone programs that may be used and incontestable on good TV of sophistication. they're memrise, duolingo, quizlet and alternative helpful tools that have become one in all the highest method of learning a remote language.

In order to grant example for those instructional apps I need to settle on duolingo to supply you, readers, with some awareness regarding them. Firstly, you must enter your g-mail or e-mail to start out your activities and so you'll run a listing of languages that area unit accessible to start learning one in all them. at that time, you'll decide your daily goal that you just are busy with it. There are a unit even given some stories and that they can develop the amount of learners from straightforward to advanced. Besides them you'll be able to mark yourself by seeing your improvement method.

The cyclical co-dependence, co-influence, and co-production of technology and society on the other (technology upon culture and vice versa) is referred to as technology and society or technology and culture. From the very beginning of humankind, when simple tools were invented, this synergistic relationship continues into current technologies like the printing press and computers. The question of whether technology is a boon or a curse for society has always been a hot-button issue. Technology has a huge effect on our culture, traditions, and social values. It is categorized as having an effect on our society today and having an effect on human activities. Technology not only increased humans' life span but also the way how

we live . Values, norms, and practices reflect a society's culture. Individuals are a reflection of culture's perceptions, practices, and values, as is the transfer of technology. Language, art, mobility, education, and religion are just a few of the fundamental aspects of our cultures that technology has had a significant impact on. Culture of a local area goes about as a norm for seeing, judging and assessing the innovation. The direction of cultural development is determined by technology, which has an impact on all cultural components. Technology must be compatible with the social and cultural conditions of the community in order to occupy the larger cultural dimension; otherwise, there will be conflict between technological advancement and the preservation of cultural values. People can express themselves freely in a technical world that transcends their ethnicity, age, or level of education with a rational balance. It is used by people to fulfill their fantasies, but a lack of restrictions, rules, or consequences may lead to a cultural decline.

Conclusion. As a conclusion I will say that the vitality of digital technologies within the sphere of education is painfully widened in today's day. It helps learners to increase their data will lighten lecturers work likewise. They are important not only in education, but also in the life of society. Through digital technologies, many people's problems become easier. Both time and money are saved. As a result, society has also become digital.

The idea of a digital culture is about how the internet and technology are changing how people interact with one another. It's how we act, think, and communicate with others in society. A digital culture is the result of disruptive technological innovation and the endless persuasive technology that surrounds us. Although it can be applied to a variety of topics, the overarching theme remains the same: the connection between technology and people.

It is appropriate to tell about its benefits as well as its harmful aspects. It should be said that digital technologies, in addition to saving time, have distanced people from each other. Face-to-face relationships have decreased. They did not

want to act. In a word, they became lazy. Digital technologies made humanity passive. Especially this situation had a significant impact on the lives and minds of young people. Because they use digital technology for bad purposes. The use of prohibited sites is a clear proof of this. Therefore, it would be appropriate if each person used each thing in his own way.

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